

Heterocyclic Compounds: XI. Studies in Oxazole Derivatives

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A number of new azlactones have been synthesised by the application of the Erlenmeyer reaction on aromatic aldehydes. Several reactions of the azlactones leading to the preparation of phenylacetic acids, benzoylaminocinnamic acids, isoquinoline, imidazole and oxidiazine derivatives have been described.

It is well known that 5(4)-oxazolones or azlactones are valuable intermediates in the synthesis of a variety of compounds. The present work describes the synthesis of some new azlactones and their reactions to yield various compounds some of which were required for another research project.

The different azlactones were obtained by an Erlenmeyer synthesis from the aromatic aldehydes (I to XV) which were prepared by the Gattermann reaction on different xyleneols as described by Agarwal *et al.*¹.

In all cases, the hydroxyl group of the azalactones was acetylated under the conditions of the Erlenmeyer reaction. In some cases, two isomeric azlactones were obtained, which were separated by difference in their solubility in benzene. Both gave the same analytical data and an identical phenylacetic acid on hydrolysis followed by oxidation. As expected, the *trans* isomer showed a higher melting point and a higher absorption in the U.V. spectrum.

In the case of the aldehyde (I) in addition to the azalactone (XVI), two other products A and B were isolated. The product A was assigned the structure as a benzamido-coumarin derivative (L) on the basis of its I.R. spectrum.

The product "B" was free from nitrogen and insoluble in sodium bicarbonate. It dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution in cold and could be precipitated by the addition of an acid. It did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, but yielded a crystalline 2, 4-DNP. From the analysis of B and the derivative, no definite structure could be assigned to it.

The azlactone XVI from aldehyde (I) on alkaline hydrolysis followed by oxidation with hydrogen peroxide afforded the phenylacetic and (XXXVII) Purification of the latter for analytical purposes involved repeated crystallisations and hence to establish its structure beyond doubt it was ethylated with ethyl iodide and anhydrous potassium carbonate. The resulting ester was hydrolysed with alkali to yield 3,4-dimethyl-2-ethoxyphenylacetic acid (XXXVIII) which was identical with that prepared from the azalactone of the aldehyde (II).

The aldehyde III on an Erlenmeyer reaction, afforded two corresponding azlactone derivatives (XVIII). They were identified as *cis* and *trans* isomers by their melting point as well as the spectra. All attempts to isolate the α -keto acid, an intermediate in the formation of the phenylacetic acid from the azlactones were unsuccessful.

The azlactone XVIII on mild alkaline hydrolysis afforded the appropriate benzoylamino-cinnamic acid (XXXI). Its methyl ester on cyclisation with phosphorous oxychloride yielded the expected isoquinoline derivative (LIV). However, our attempts at decarboxylation of the acid XXXI failed to yield a definite compound. Whereas the treatment of the azlactone (XVIII) with ammonia in the presence of potassium carbonate and sodium hydroxide as described by Galat² yielded the expected imidazole derivative (LI) that with hydrogen sulphide in the presence of sodium methoxide gave an ester found to be identical (mmp) with the methyl ester of XXXI. Action of hydrazine hydrate on the azlactone (XVIII) afforded the hydrazide (LII). The attempted cyclisation of the hydrazide to obtain the corresponding oxidiazine, afforded instead, a geometric isomer of the hydrazide. However, both the isomeric hydrazides when heated over their melting points afforded the identical oxidiazine derivative (LVII).

Imidazole:

- LI — $R_1=R_2=CH_3$; $R_3=OH$; $R_4=H$
 LV — $R_1=R_4=CH_3$; $R_3=OH$; $R_2=H$
 LVIII — $R_2=R_4=CH_3$; $R_3=OH$; $R_1=H$

Hydrazide:

- LII — $R_1=R_2=CH_3$; $R_3=OH$; $R_4=H$
 LXII — $R_2=R_4=CH_3$; $R_3=OH$; $R_1=H$

Dihydroisoquinoline:

Oxidiazine:

The aldehydes, 3,5-dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (IV) and 2,4-dimethyl-5-hydroxybenzaldehyde (VI) afforded the corresponding azlactones XIX and XXI as usual. The azlactone XIX on hydrolysis followed by oxidation yielded the phenylacetic acid XL. Its structure was established by ethylating it to 3,5-dimethyl-2-ethoxyphenylacetic acid which was synthesised from the ethylated aldehyde IV.

The mild alkaline hydrolysis of azlactone XXIII yielded the benzoylaminocinnamic acid (XXXII), whereas its treatment with ammonia in the presence of alkali afforded an imidazolone derivative (LV).

The isomeric azlactones XXIV yielded the same phenylacetic acid (XLIV) and also gave the same benzoylaminocinnamic acid (XXXIII) on mild hydrolysis with alkali. The latter on treatment with hydroiodic acid, red phosphorous and acetic anhydride as described in literature³ failed to yield any pure product.

The isomeric azlactones XXV which yielded the identical phenylacetic acid XLV, on mild hydrolysis afforded the same benzoylaminocinnamic acid XXXIV, the reduction of which with sodium amalgam according to the method of Fischer⁴ afforded the corresponding benzoylaminopropionic acid LVI. The latter underwent cyclisation when heated with phosphorus oxychloride to afford the dihydroisoquinoline carboxylic acid LVII. The latter was characterised by the preparation of its picrate.

The azlactone XXV with ammonia and alkali gave the imidazolone derivative LVIII (I.R.).

Reaction of hydrazine hydrate on the azlactone XXV gave the hydrazide LXII which on treatment with nitrous acid surprisingly yielded the starting azlactone (XXV) (mmp.). The azlactone on treatment with hydrogen sulphide in the presence of sodium methoxide yielded two products. The first product contained nitrogen and its analytical results indicated the structure as the methyl ester of the benzoylaminocinnamic acid LX. This was confirmed by its synthesis via esterifying the benzoylaminocinnamic acid (mmp). The second product contained nitrogen, sulphur and a carboxyl group. From its analysis and by analogy with the work of previous workers⁵, it was assigned the structure as a thiazole derivative LIX. This was further confirmed by its hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid when the expected mercaptoamino acid LXI was obtained.

Mild hydrolysis of the azlactone XXVI yielded benzoylaminocinnamic acid XXXV, which when reduced with sodium amalgam gave a colourless oil which could not be assigned a definite structure as variable results were obtained on analysis.

The azlactone XVIII on vigorous hydrolysis yielded an acid identified as α -keto acid LXIII and characterised by the preparation of its 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative. The keto acid on oxidation with hydrogen peroxide yielded, instead of the phenylacetic acid, a water soluble phenol identified as 3, 5-xyleneol(mmp). The mild hydrolysis of the azlactone failed to yield a definite compound. The azlactone when reduced with sodium amalgam as described by Fischer⁴ yielded a colourless oil. It contained nitrogen and possessed a phenolic smell. No definite structure could be assigned to it.

The azlactone derivative from 4, 6-dimethyl-2-methoxy-benzaldehyde was obtained as an oil. The oil when heated in a sealed tube with ammonia and methanol to obtain an indole derivative as described by Hill and Robinson⁶ did not yield any definite product.

3. C. R. Harrington and G. Barger, *Biochem. J.*, 1927, **21**, 109.
4. E. Fischer, *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 3638.
5. V. du Vigneaud *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1948, **176**, 907.
6. P. Hill and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 486.

Mild hydrolysis of the azlactone XXVIII afforded the benzoylaminocinnamic acid XXXVI which could be decarboxylated to the styrylamide LXV. Reduction of the benzoylaminocinnamic acid with sodium amalgam yielded the corresponding precipicnic acid LXIV.

4-Ethoxy-2-methoxybenzaldehyde⁷ (XIV) yielded the azlactone XXIX on condensing it with hippuric acid. The azlactone was degraded to the corresponding phenylacetic acid XLVIII by hydrolysis followed by oxidation. Another phenylacetic acid XLIX, 2-ethoxy-3-methoxyphenylacetic acid was synthesised by the hydrolysis and oxidation of the appropriate azlactone XXX, the latter having been prepared from 2-ethoxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde XV obtained by the ethylation of *o*-vanilin.

EXPERIMENTAL

The aldehyde from the different xylenols were prepared by the application of the Gattermann reaction described in literature¹.

General Method for the preparation of azlactones or 5(4)-oxazolones: A mixture of aldehyde (9 g.), hippuric acid (12 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (6 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 ml.) was heated on a water bath for 45 minutes. The colour of the reaction mixture changed to dark yellow. It was left overnight after adding alcohol (20 ml.). The yellow solid which separated was filtered, washed free of hippuric acid and sodium acetate. It was dried and crystallised to yield the azlactone. In some cases two isomers were isolated.

General Method for the preparation of benzoylaminocinnamic acid: The azlactone (10 g.) was mixed with 10% sodium hydroxide (100 ml.) and heated on a water bath for half an hour till all the azlactone dissolved. The reaction mixture was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid to yield a colourless solid. It was filtered, washed and dried to get the benzoylaminocinnamic acid derivative.

General Method for the preparation of phenylacetic acids: The azlactone (8 g.) was hydrolysed with 10% sodium hydroxide (80 ml.) by refluxing on an oil bath at 120-130° for several hours, till the evolution of ammonia ceased. The reaction mixture was mixed with 40% sodium hydroxide (8 ml.) and oxidised with 15% hydrogen peroxide (8 ml.) at 0-10°. After allowing it to stand overnight, it was acidified and then extracted with warm benzene.

The solid obtained on removal of benzene was esterified with methanol and working up the reaction mixture afforded a mixture of methyl esters of benzoic acid and phenylacetic acid derivative. The methyl ester of phenylacetic acid derivative was separated by vacuum distillation.

The oily ester (2 g.) was hydrolysed with 10% sodium hydroxide (20 ml.) On acidification a solid phenylacetic acid derivative separated. It was usually crystallised from water.

7. A. Sonn and E. Patschke, *Ber.*, 1925, **58B**, 1700.

8. H. Schumolfuss and W. Peschke, *Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 2591.

9. J. S. Buck *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1939, **60**, 1799.

2-Phenyl-4-(2-acetoxy-3, 4-dimethylbenzylidene)-5(4)-oxazolone (XVI) and 3-benzoylamino-7, 8-dimethylcoumarin (L). The 3,4-dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (I, 9 g.) on condensing with hippuric acid yielded a yellow solid (3 g.) along with the azlactone XVI which crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 208° (Found: C, 73.9; H, 5.3. $C_{18}H_{15}NO_3$ requires C, 73.7; H, 5.15%). It was identified as 3-benzoylamino-7,8-dimethyl-coumarin (L). The I.R. absorption spectrum of the compound confirms the structure. (γ_{max} 3408 cm^{-1} (NH), 1706; (CO), 1674 : 1523 cm^{-1} (CONH).

The filtrate from the above was extracted with ether and the ether extract washed free of acetic acid, hippuric acid and sodium acetate. Removal of the solvent after drying left an oil, to which alcohol (20 ml.) was added and then the solution was left overnight in a refrigerator, when a yellow solid (3.5 g.) separated. Crystallisation from alcohol-petroleum ether (40-60°) mixture afforded colourless plates, of XVI, m.p. 137°.

1-Hydro-2-phenyl-4-(2, 3 dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzylidene)-5-imidazolone(LI): A mixture of azlactone (XVIII, 1 g.), absolute alcohol (20 ml.) and ammonium hydroxide (5 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath for 15 min. Potassium carbonate (500 mg.) dissolved in little water was then added and the refluxing continued for 1 hr. more. Sodium hydroxide (25% ; 8 ml.) was then added to the mixture and the boiling continued for another 30 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and acidified with acetic acid, when a yellow solid separated (710 mg.). It was crystallised from ethyl acetate in needles, m.p. 286° (decomp.). (Found: C, 74.1; H, 5.5. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires C, 74.1; H, 5.48%).

Its picrate was crystallised from alcohol in red needles, m.p. 204°. (Found: N, 13.1. $C_{24}H_{19}N_5O_9$ requires N, 13.43%).

α -Benzoylamino- β -(2,3-dimethyl-1-4-hydroxyphenyl)-acrylohydrazide (LII). To a well stirred mixture of azlactone (XVIII, 2 g.) in absolute alcohol (75 ml.) was added 80% hydrazine hydrate (0.9 ml.) in drops during a period of half an hour. On diluting the reaction mixture, the hydrazide (LII; 1.5 g.) separated out. It was crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. 166° (Found: N, 12.6. $C_{18}H_{19}N_3O_3$ requires N, 12.9 %).

4[(2,3-Dimethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-methyl]-6-phenyl-2H-1,3,5-oxidiazine-2-one (LIII): The above acrylohydrazide (LII; 1 g.) was heated in a hard glass test tube. At the temperature 160-165°, the acrylohydrazide melted. As the temperature rose to 190-95° it solidified again when the heating was stopped. It was crystallised from alcohol in orange prisms (370 mg.), m.p. 249° (Found: C, 70.2; H, 5.5. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_3$ requires C, 70.1; H, 5.2 %).

Action of nitrous acid on the acrylohydrazide LII: The hydrazide (LII; 500 mg.) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (15 ml.) was added dropwise at 0° to a solution of sodium nitrite (250 mg.) in minimum amount of water when an orange solid separated (300 mg.) It was crystallised from benzene in yellow needles, m.p. 198° (Found: N, 12.5. $C_{18}H_{19}N_3O_3$ requires N, 12.9%).

It was identified as the higher melting isomer of the above acrylohydrazide, since on heating at 210° in an oil bath, the same oxidiazine was obtained, which was also obtained from the lower melting isomer (166°) of the above hydrazide.

Action of hydrogen sulphide on 2-phenyl-4-(4-acetoxy-2,3-dimethyl-benzylidene)-5(4)-oxazolone (XVIII) in the presence of sodium methoxide: The azlactone (1.5 g.) was dissolved in sodium methoxide (20 ml.) previously saturated with hydrogen sulphide. To this solution hydrogen sulphide was bubbled for 10 hr. at 0-20°. The reaction mixture was then acidified with hydrochloric acid to get a white precipitate. It was filtered, washed and dried. The solid (1 g.) was crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 173°. (Found: C, 69.8; H, 5.8. $C_{19}H_{20}NO_4$ requires C, 70.1; H, 5.8%).

It was identified as the methyl ester of α -benzoylamino- β -(2,3-dimethyl-4-hydroxy)-cinnamic acid as indicated by the mixed melting point determination with ester prepared as usual from the cinnamic acid derivative XXXI.

5,6-Dimethyl-7-hydroxy-1-phenylisoquinoline-3-carboxylic ester (LIV): The methyl ester of cinnamic acid derivative (200 mg.) was refluxed with 2 ml. of phosphorus oxychloride on a water bath for 1 hr. when an orange solid separated. The reaction mixture was cooled and decomposed with ice cold water. The solid obtained (130 mg.) was filtered, washed and crystallised from alcohol in yellow prisms, m.p. 263° (Found: C, 74.5; H, 5.4. $C_{19}H_{17}NO_3$ requires C, 74.3; H, 5.5%).

1-Hydro-2-phenyl-4-(2,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzylidene)-5-imidazolone (LV): The azlactone XXIII (1 g.) was converted into the imidazolone LV (700 mg.) by refluxing with potassium carbonate, ammonia and sodium hydroxide in the usual manner. The yellow solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 289° (Found: C, 73.9; H, 5.5. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires C, 74.0; H, 5.5%).

α -Benzoylamino- β -(3,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-propionic acid (LVI): The benzoylamino-cinnamic acid XXXIV (7 g.) was dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide (70 ml.) The solution was cooled to 10-20° and 10% sodium amalgam (18 g.) was added in small portions during a period of half an hour with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was left overnight and acidified with cooling to get a solid (4.1 g.). It was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in needles, m.p. 210°. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 6.1. $C_{18}H_{19}NO_4$ requires C, 69.0; H, 6.0%).

6,8-Dimethyl-3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-1-phenylisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (LVII): The propionic acid LVI (200 mg.) was cyclised by refluxing with phosphorus oxychloride (2 ml.) on a water bath at 70-80° for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and decomposed with 25 ml. of ice cold water. The solid (105 mg.) obtained was crystallised from chloroform in yellow prisms, m.p. 196° (Found: C, 73.3; H, 5.8. $C_{18}H_{17}NO_3$ requires C, 73.2; H, 5.7%).

It yielded a picrate which crystallised in yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 234-235° (decomp.).

1-Hydro-2-phenyl-4-(3,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzylidene)-5-imidazolone (LVIII): The azlactone XXV (500 mg.) was converted into LVIII as described before.

The imidazolone was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 275° (decomp.). (Found: C, 74.3; H, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires C, 74.0; H, 5.4%); $\gamma_{\max}$ 3412 cm^{-1} (OH); 3190 cm^{-1} (NH); 1702 cm^{-1} (CO) 1640 cm^{-1} (CN).

Its picrate crystallised from ethyl acetate in orange needles, m.p. 270°. (Found: N, 13.6. $C_{24}H_{19}N_3O_9$ requires N, 13.4%).

4,5-Dihydro-2-phenyl-5-(3,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-thiazole-4-carboxylic acid (LIX) and methyl ester of α -benzoylamino- β -(3,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxy)-cinnamic acid (LX): The azlactone XXV (1.5 g.) was mixed with sodium methoxide (20 ml.) (prepared by dissolving 300 mg. of sodium in 20 ml. of methanol) previously saturated with hydrogen sulphide. The mixture was cooled to 10-20° and hydrogen sulphide was bubbled for 10 hr.

The reaction mixture was acidified to give a solid (1.2 g.). The solid on crystallisation gave two fractions.

(i) Yellow globules (300 mg.) separated first from benzene. It was crystallised from the same solvent in globules, m.p. 143°. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{17}NO_3S$ requires C, 66.0; H, 5.2%). The product was assigned the structure as LIX, since it was soluble in sodium bicarbonate and gave test for sulphur.

(ii) The second fraction (800 mg.) crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 203° (Found: C, 70.0; H, 6.0. $C_{19}H_{19}NO_4$ requires C, 70.1; H, 5.8%).

It was assigned the structure as LX by a mixed melting point with the sample synthesised by esterifying the cinnamic acid derivative XXXIV.

Hydrochloride of α -amino- β -mercapto- β -(3,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-propionic acid (LXI): The foregoing thiazole (100 mg.) was hydrolysed with 10 ml. of concentrated hydrochloric acid by refluxing for 8 hr. On cooling yellow solid (65 mg.) was separated. It was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 186° (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{16}ClNO_3S$ requires N, 5.0%).

α -Benzoylamino- β -(3,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-acrylohydrazide (LXII): The azlactone XXV (4 g.) on treatment with hydrazine hydrate yielded LXII (2.6 g.) crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 146° (Found: N 12.8. $C_{18}H_{19}N_3O_3$ requires N, 12.9%).

4,6-Dimethyl-2-hydroxyphenylpyruvic acid (LXIII): The azlactone XXVII (5 g.) was hydrolysed with 10% sodium hydroxide (50 ml.) till the evolution of ammonia ceased. The resulting mixture was saturated with sulphur dioxide at 10-15° when benzoic acid precipitated. It was filtered off and the boiling filtrate acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. On cooling the pyruvic acid LXIII separated out as white solid (1.5 g.), m.p. 121-124°.

Its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from benzene in red needles, m.p. 147° (Found: N, 14.1. $C_{17}H_{16}N_4O_7$ requires N, 14.4%).

α -Benzoylamino- β -(2,6-dimethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-propionic acid (LXIV): The azlactone XXVIII (5.5 g.) was reduced with 10% sodium amalgam (18 g.). The solid propionic acid derivative LXIV (2.8 g.) was crystallised from ethyl acetate in prisms, m.p. 206°. (Found: C, 69.3; H, 6.3. $C_{18}H_{19}NO_4$ requires C, 69.0; H, 6.0 %).

N-Benzoyl-2,6-dimethyl-4-hydroxy styrylamide (LXV): The cinnamic acid XXXVI (100 mg.) was decarboxylated by refluxing with copper powder (100 mg.) and quinoline

TABLE I

No.	Benzaldehyde Name	No.	Azlactone m.p.	Crystallised from	Crystals	Formula	Analysis					
							Found	Calculated	C	H	N	N
I	 Benzaldehyde	XVI	137°	Alcohol-Petroleum ether (40-60°)	Colourless Plates	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄	C 72.0	H 5.5	—	71.6	5.11	—
II	 Benzaldehyde	XVII	152°	Ethylacetate	Yellow Needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ NO ₃	74.8	5.9	—	74.7	5.9	—
III	 Benzaldehyde	XVIII	230° and 159° trans λ _{max} 220 (log ε 4.0) & 310 (log ε 3.77). cis λ _{max} 225 (log ε 3.85) & 285 (log ε 3.75) (Lit ⁸ m.p. 183°)	Toluene Benzene	Yellow Needles , ,	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄ -do-	71.6 71.7	5.3 5.2	—	71.6 71.6	5.11 5.11	—
IV	 Benzaldehyde	XIX	Oil		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
V	 Benzaldehyde	XX	180	Alcohol	Yellow Needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ NO ₃	74.5	6.0	—	74.7	5.9	—
VI	 Benzaldehyde	XXI	153	Benzene-Petroleum ether (40-60°)	Yellow Needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄	71.4	5.2	—	71.6	5.11	—

TABLE I (Contd.)

No.	Benzaldehyde Name	No.	Azlactone m.p.	Crystallised from	Crystals	Formula	Analysis					
							Found	Calculated	C	H	N	
VII	R ₁ =OH; R ₂ , R ₅ =CH ₃ ; R ₃ , R ₄ =H	XXII	175°	Ethylacetate	Yellow Needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄	71.9	5.2	—	71.6	5.11	—
VIII	R ₃ =OH; R ₁ , R ₄ =CH ₃ ; R ₂ , R ₅ =OH	XXIII	225 and 165° λ _{max} trans 235 (log ε 4.35); 320 (log ε 4.08) λ _{max} cis 215 (log ε 4.28); 310 (log ε 4.05)	Benzene Benzene- Petroleum ether (40-60°)	Yellow Needles " "	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄ -do-	71.4 71.5	5.2 5.3	—	71.6	5.11	—
IX	R ₂ =OH; R ₁ , R ₃ =CH ₃ ; R ₄ , R ₅ =H	XXIV	212° and 188° trans λ _{max} 230 (log ε 3.88); 290 (log ε 3.5) cis λ _{max} 225 (log ε 3.80); 290 (log ε 3.68)	Toluene Benzene- Petroleum ether (40-60°)	Yellow Needles " "	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄ -do-	71.5 71.7	5.0 5.3	—	71.6	5.11	—
X	R ₃ =OH; R ₂ , R ₄ =CH ₃ ; R ₁ , R ₅ =H	XXV	192° and 188° (Lit. ⁸ , M.P. 189°)	Toluene Benzene- Petroleum ether (40-60°)	Yellow Prisms Yellow Needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄ -do-	71.3 71.4	5.1 5.1	—	71.6	5.11	—
XI	R ₁ =OH; R ₃ , R ₄ =CH ₃ ; R ₂ , R ₅ =H	XXVI	163°	Ethylacetate	Yellow Needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄	71.9	5.4	—	71.6	5.11	—
XII	R ₁ =OH; R ₃ , R ₅ +CH ₃ ; R ₂ , R ₄ =H	XXVII	119°	Benzene- Petroleum ether (40-60°)	Yellow Needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄	71.6	5.2	—	71.6	5.11	—
XIII	R ₃ =OH; R ₁ , R ₅ =CH ₃ ; R ₂ , R ₄ =H	XXVIII	162°	Ethylacetate	Yellow Needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₄	71.4	5.1	—	71.6	5.11	—
XIV	R ₁ =OCH ₃ ; R ₃ =OC ₂ H ₅ ; R ₂ , R ₄ , R ₅ =H	XXIX	159°	Benzene	Yellow Prisms	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₄	—	—	—	4.6	—	4.3
XV	R ₁ =OC ₂ H ₅ ; R ₂ =OCH ₃ ; R ₃ , R ₄ , R ₅ =H	XXX	172° (Lit. ⁹ m.p. 140°)	Benzene	Yellow Needles	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₄	—	—	—	4.7	—	4.3

TABLE II

Phenylacetic acid

 α -Benzylaminocinnamic acid

No.	No.	α -Benzylaminocinnamic acid		Phenylacetic acid		Formula	m.p.	Crystallised from and crystals	Phenylacetic acid Crystallised from and crystals	Analysis		Analysis				
		Crystallised from and crystals	m.p.	Formula	Found					Calculated	Found	Calculated				
XVI	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—			
XVII	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—			
XVIII	XXXI	236° (Lit ⁸ m.p.236°)	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₄	69.2	5.4	69.4	5.5	XXXIX	118°	Sublimed	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	66.8	6.3	66.6	6.6
XIX	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	XL	114°	Benzene-Pet. ether needles (40-60°)	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	66.8	6.4	66.6	6.6
XX	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	XLI	118°	Water-needles	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₃	69.2	7.7	69.2	7.7
XXII	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	XLII	78°	Water-needles	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	66.5	6.8	66.6	6.6
XXIII	XXXII	239° (Lit ⁸ m.p. 239°)	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₄	69.3	5.4	69.4	5.5	XLIII	116°	Benzene-Pet. ether (40-60°) -needles	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	66.7	6.3	66.6	6.6
XXIV	XXXIII	221°	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₄	69.4	5.3	69.4	5.5	XLIV	113°	Sublimed	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	66.9	6.8	66.6	6.6

TABLE II (Contd.)

No.	Azlactone	No.	m.p.	Crystallised from and crystals			Formula	Analysis		m.p.	Phenylacetic acid Crystallised from and crystals			Formula	Analysis		
				Found	Calculated	No.		C	H		Found	Calculated	Found		Calculated		
XXV		XXXIV	216°	Alcohol-needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₄	69.5	5.6	69.4	5.5	XLV	125°	Benzene-needles	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	66.4	6.8	66.6	6.6
XXVI		XXXV	214°	Alcohol-needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₄	69.5	5.4	69.4	5.5	XLVI	123°	Benzene-Petroleum ether (40-60°) needles	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	66.8	6.3	66.6	6.6
XXVIII		XXXVI	233°	Prisms	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₄	69.7	5.7	69.4	5.5	XLVII	119°	Water-needles	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	66.5	6.6	66.6	6.6
XXIX		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	XLVIII	110°	Water-needles	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄	62.5	6.6	62.8	6.6
XXX		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	XLIX	77°	Benzene-Pet.ether (40-60°) needles	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄	62.5	6.6	62.8	6.6

(2 ml.) for 4 hr. The resulting mixture was decomposed with ice cold hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. A solid (55 m.) was obtained on removal of ether. It was purified by sublimation under vacuum, m.p. 208°. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 6.5. $C_{17}H_{17}NO_2$ requires C, 76.4; H, 6.8%).

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